

Fashion Consumption for Fashion Innovators: A Study of Fashion Consumption Behavior of Innovators and Non-Innovators

Vaishali P. Joshi, Pallav Joshi

Abstract—The objective of this study is to examine the differences fashion innovators and non-fashion innovators in their fashion consumption behavior in terms of their pre-purchase behavior, purchase behavior and post purchase behavior. The questionnaire was distributed to a female college student for data collection for achieving the objective of the first part of the study. Question-related to fashion innovativeness and fashion consumption behavior was asked. The sample was comprised of 81 college females ages 18 through 30 who were attending Business Management degree. A series of attitude questions was used to categorize respondents on the Innovativeness Scale. 32 respondents with a score of 21 and above were designated as Fashion innovators and the remainder (49) as Non-fashion innovators. Findings showed that there exist significant differences between innovators and non-innovators in their fashion consumption behavior. Data was analyzed through frequency distribution table. Many differences were found in the behavior of innovators and non-innovators in terms of their pre-purchase, actual purchase, and post-purchase behavior.

Keywords—Consumption behavior, fashion, innovativeness, frequency distribution table.

I. INTRODUCTION

FASHION innovativeness is said to one's willingness to adopt or try or purchase any new fashion item. Previous research investigated the relationship between lifestyle and purchase behavior of high fashion groups. According to [1] several characteristics of fashion innovators are as follows: they are more likely to be younger, they have a higher education level and higher income. Moreover according to [2], fashion innovators are more involved in social activities and personal interaction.

Fashion innovators tend to be heavy shoppers in terms of both money spent in the purchase of clothes and the number of clothes [3]. The purchase behavior of fashion innovators has been examined in terms of the fashion process. Previous research has suggested that the fashion process is a normal S-shaped curve consisted of four stages. According to [4], the fashion process composed of four stages as (i) introduction stage- the product is launched in the market (ii) growth stage- the products' sales increases (iii) maturity stage- sales growth continues and demand decrease and (iv) decline- where sales of the product begin to decrease. In this fashion process,

Vaishali P Joshi and Pallav Joshi are research scholars at Gujarat Technological University, Ahmedabad, India (phone: +919428157720, +919428251620; e-mail: vaishalipjoshi15 @ gmail.com, Pallav_9 @ yahoo.com).

fashion innovators try of purchase the new product or style at the introduction stage while non-fashion innovators purchase at the growth or maturity stage.

The relative length of each stage in fashion process is determined by numerous characteristics of the fashion items. According to [5] the more complex and unique the fashion item, the more costly it is, which in turn causes greater the length of each stage. In other words, we can say that the more unique and complex fashion items make the distance large between fashion innovators and non-fashion innovators in their purchase behavior.

Due to increased competition in the fashion industry, the phenomenon of fashion consumption has become very complex. So, it becomes very important to study the behavior of shoppers at different situations i.e. before purchase, actual purchase and after purchase. This study will highlight some important factors, which will be very helpful for the marketing firms to grab the shoppers' attention not only during actual purchase but also before and after purchase.

II. PROCEDURE

A. Objectives of the Study

Research main objective: The purpose of the study is to investigate differences between fashion innovators and non-fashion innovators in their fashion consumption behavior.

Research Sub-objective:

1. To study differences between fashion innovators and non-fashion innovators in terms of their pre-purchase behavior
2. To study differences between fashion innovators and non-fashion innovators in terms of their actual purchase behavior.
3. To study differences between fashion innovators and non-fashion innovators in terms of their post-purchase behavior

B. Development of Instrument

This paper was planned to examine differences between fashion innovators and non-fashion innovators in their fashion consumption practices.

The independent variable in this research study was fashion innovativeness, and the dependent variable was fashion consumption practices. For fashion innovativeness, variable respondents were divided into three categories: high, medium, and low fashion innovators. Fashion consumption practices were defined as pre-purchase behavior, purchase behavior and the post-purchase behavior in the process of fashion

consumption. For data collection, a structured questionnaire was developed.

The questionnaire consisted of four parts: 1) a fashion innovativeness scale 2) questions related to pre-purchase behavior 3) questions related to actual purchase behavior 4) questions related to post-purchase behavior

1. Fashion Innovativeness Scale

To measure the fashion innovativeness of the respondents, Innovativeness Scale [6] was utilized. This scale consisted of total six statements. Respondents were asked to rate each statement on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1= strongly disagree to 5= strongly agree. Those respondents who achieved a score of 21 or above were considered as fashion innovators. Otherwise, they were considered as non-fashion innovators. Statement 1 and 5, were assigned reversed rating to judge the result of direction-of-item wording on the responses.

2. Pre-Purchase Behavior

In this part of the questionnaire, questions related to respondents' pre-purchase behavior was asked, which consisted of two items. They are 1) Motivation to purchase fashion apparel and 2) Source of acquiring information about fashion apparel.

3. Actual Purchase Behavior

In this part of the questionnaire, questions related to respondents' actual purchase behavior was asked, which consisted of two items. They are 1) respondents' preferred type of store for the purchase and 2) Attributes of fashion apparel which respondents' prefer for purchase.

4. Post-Purchase Behavior

In this part of the questionnaire, questions related to respondents' post-purchase behavior was asked, which consisted of three items. They are 1) duration of wearing any fashion apparel by the respondents 2) reasons behind not wearing any fashion apparel by the respondents and 3) ways of disposing of any fashion apparel not worn by the respondents.

5. Demographic Information

The last part of the questionnaire consisted of the demographic profile of the respondents, which consisted of the questions related to their age, education, approximate shopping budget for fashion apparel per month.

C. Pilot Test

To better construct the questionnaire, a pilot study was conducted. A sample questionnaire was distributed to ten female college students, aged 18-27. From the pilot study, it was confirmed that the instructions and questions were clear. The final questionnaire is shown in Appendix A.

D. Data Collection

College female students enrolled in Masters in Business Administration were selected as a sample through convenience sampling. A total of 108 questionnaires were distributed, from which 81 questionnaires were completely filled by the

respondents.

III. DATA ANALYSIS

Collected data were properly coded and enter into a computer. MS Excel was used to analyze the data. Based upon total score of respondents' on the fashion innovativeness scale, they were categorized into two groups: i) fashion innovators and ii) non-fashion innovators (as shown in Table I).

TABLE I
 DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY FASHION INNOVATOR GROUPS

Group	N	%	Mean	S.D.
Non-Fashion Innovators	49	60.49	1.73	1.32
Fashion Innovators	32	39.50	4.19	1.20
Total	81	100.00		

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The presentation of findings is composed of three sections: i) pre-purchase behavior, ii) actual purchase behavior and iii) post-purchase behavior.

A. Section I: Pre-Purchase Behavior

"The buying process starts when the buyer recognizes a problem or need triggered by internal or external stimuli [7]. In other words, we can say that there is always a reason for the consumers to purchase or try something item, product or service. This need for new purchase can be based on some motive." A need becomes a motive when it is aroused to a sufficient level of intensity to drive us to act [7]. This study identified the differences in the motivation for the purchase of new fashion apparel between fashion innovators and non-innovators, as shown in Table II.

It was found that an urge for new and latest style or fashionable apparel is the most important motivation for the innovators to purchase the new fashion apparel, whereas, in the case of the non-innovators price factor is most important. In other words, we can say that non-innovators are more inclined towards the sale and promotion for the purchase of fashion apparel, and for them, new style or fashionable does not play a significant role.

TABLE II
 MOTIVATION TO PURCHASE

Motivation	Fashion innovators Frequency (%)	Non-fashion Innovators Frequency (%)
Personal enjoyment	7 (21.87)	7 (14.28)
Social occasions	4 (12.5)	11 (22.44)
Seasonal changes	6 (18.75)	10 (20.40)
Sale season	2 (6.25)	15 (30.61)
For latest style/fashion	13 (40.62)	6 (12.24)
Total	32 (100)	49 (100)

Whenever we think or plan to purchase any new item or product, we always search for information related to that item or product, knowingly or unknowingly. There are numerous sources of information available to the consumers. According to [7], there are four major sources of information: i) personal, ii) commercial iii) public and iv) experiential. Based on these information sources, we have identified which source of

information is most important for the fashion innovators and for the non-innovators, as shown in Table III.

It was concluded that fashion innovators depend heavily on fashion shows or fashion TV programs for acquiring the information about the latest fashion in apparel. But for non-innovators the case is different. They rely on the advice of other women on fashion trends and styles. Also, it was found that the second most important information source for innovators is observation. Hence we can conclude that non-innovators are dependable for fashion information and more involved in observation in social gatherings or any other events.

TABLE III
SOURCE OF ACQUIRING INFORMATION BEFORE PURCHASE

Information source	Fashion Innovators Frequency (%)	Non-fashion Innovators Frequency (%)
Catalogues	6 (18.75)	0 (0)
Observation	1 (3.12)	10 (20.40)
Store window display	1 (3.12)	5 (10.20)
Magazines	5 (15.62)	2 (4.08)
Friends	0 (0)	7 (14.28)
Fashion shows/Fashion TV	11 (34.37)	1 (2.04)
Salespersons	0 (0)	4 (8.16)
Family members	0 (0)	6 (12.24)
Internet	5 (15.62)	3 (6.12)
Fashion experts	3 (9.3)	0 (0)
Advice from other women	0 (0)	11 (22.44)
Total	32 (100)	49 (100)

B. Section 2: Actual Purchase

This section highlights the major store destination for the innovators and non-innovators in their purchase of fashion apparel. According to [8], the classification of on-site fashion retailers includes Specialty stores, Department stores, Fashion manufacture's outlets, Discount operations and Boutiques. Based on this classification, we had identified the most preferred store for the innovators and non-innovators, as shown in Table IV. We can find from the table that Specialty store and Department store is the most preferred store for innovators and non-innovators respectively.

TABLE IV
PREFERRED STORES FOR PURCHASE

Information source	Fashion innovators Frequency (%)	Non-fashion Innovators Frequency (%)
Department store	8 (25.00)	17 (34.69)
Discount store	2 (6.25)	10 (20.40)
Specialty store	13 (40.62)	3 (6.12)
Local brand store	3 (9.37)	14 (28.57)
Boutiques	6 (18.75)	5 (10.20)
Total	32 (100)	49 (100)

Apart from identifying the most preferred store, we have identified the most important attribute of the fashion apparel considered by innovators and non-innovators as shown in Table V. Different consumers purchase products based on the characteristics or attributes of the product. In the case of

fashion apparel purchase, the attributes of apparel can be fit, quality, brand, price, comfort, appearance, color or pattern.

We can find that apparel having the fashionable appearance is a most important attribute for the innovators and quality of the apparel for the non-innovators. Hence we can say that innovators most often give importance to their appearance and look, whereas non-innovators prefer quality, as they are less frequent in their fashion apparel purchase.

TABLE V
FASHION APPAREL ATTRIBUTES

Attributes	Fashion innovators Frequency (%)	Non-fashion Innovators Frequency (%)
Fitting	2(6.25)	6 (12.24)
Quality	3 (9.37)	10 (20.40)
Brand	3 (9.37)	2 (4.08)
Price	1 (3.12)	7 (14.28)
Comfort	4 (12.5)	7 (14.28)
Fashionable	9 (28.12)	4 (8.16)
Color	4 (12.5)	8 (16.32)
Pattern	6 (18.75)	5 (10.20)
Total	32 (100)	49 (100)

C. Section 3: Post-Purchase Behavior

This section deals with the duration to wear any fashion apparel in the case of innovators and non-innovators. We have identified the most preferred duration of wearing any fashion apparel by the innovators and non-innovators, as shown in Table VI. For innovators, the duration is not fixed for wearing any fashion apparel. And, in the case of non-innovators, the favorability of the fashion apparel is most important in term of duration to wear that fashion apparel.

TABLE VI
DURATION TO WEAR

Reasons	Fashion innovators Frequency (%)	Non-fashion Innovators Frequency (%)
Less than 1 year	3(9.37)	2 (4.08)
Between 1 year to 2 year	2 (6.25)	1 (2.04)
Between 2 year to 3 year	2 (6.25)	1 (2.04)
More than 3 years	2 (6.25)	11 (22.44)
It is not fixed	12 37.5	14 (28.57)
Depends on the favorability	11 (34.37)	20 (40.81)
Total	32 (100)	49 (100)

After identifying the duration to wear, we have identified the most preferred way of disposal of any fashion apparel by innovators as shown in Table VII. It was found that majority of the innovators always give away their fashion apparel to relatives or friends, as a way of disposing of the fashion apparel. Whereas, they save it often to wear in future and sometimes donate or keep if because of some emotional attachment. But they never sell it for a second price and never throw it away.

The most preferred way of disposal of any fashion apparel by non-innovators is as shown in Table VIII. For non-innovators, saving their fashion apparel for future use was always preferred. Also most often non-innovators give their fashion apparel to relatives of friends and also save it. The

majority of the non-innovators sell their fashion apparel sometimes at a second-hand price. And they never throw away their fashion apparel.

TABLE VII
DISPOSAL OF APPAREL: FASHION INNOVATORS

	Always 1	Often 2	Sometimes 3	Never 4	Total
Ways of disposal	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)
Donate it	5(15.62)	9 (28.12)	11 (34.37)	7(21.87)	32(100)
Emotional attachment	6 (18.72)	10 (31.25)	11 (34.37)	5(15.62)	32 (100)
Save it to wear in the coming years	9 (28.12)	12 (37.5)	7 (21.87)	5 (15.62)	32 (100)
Give it to relatives or friends	13 (40.62)	10 (31.25)	5 (15.62)	4(12.5)	32 (100)
Throw it away	5(15.62)	5 (15.62)	10 (31.25)	12 (37.5)	32 (100)
Recycle it	4 (12.5)	3 (9.37)	15 (46.87)	10 (31.25)	32 (100)
Sell it at a second hand price	0 (0)	3 (9.37)	13(40.62)	16 (50.00)	32 (100)

TABLE VIII
DISPOSAL OF APPAREL: NON-INNOVATORS

	Always 1	Often 2	Sometimes 3	Never 4	Total
Ways of disposal	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)
Donate it	5(10.20)	8(16.32)	12 (24.48)	24 (48.97)	49(100)
Emotional attachment	7 (14.28)	10 (20.40)	20 (40.81)	12 (24.48)	49(100)
Save it to wear in the coming years	24 (48.97)	11 (22.44)	8 (16.32)	5 (10.20)	49(100)
Give it to relatives or friends	3 (6.12)	13 (26.53)	20 (40.81)	14 (28.57)	49(100)
Throw it away	5(10.20)	8 (16.32)	10 (20.40)	26 (53.06)	49(100)
Recycle it	7 (14.28)	10 (20.40)	25 (20.40)	7 (14.28)	49(100)
Sell it at a second hand price	2 (4.08)	7(14.28)	27 (55.10)	13 (40.62)	49(100)

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we have examined the difference between innovators and non-innovators in their fashion consumption process. It was found from the data analysis that there exist significant differences between innovators and non-innovators in their fashion consumption behavior.

Innovators were found very be confident and independent enough in their purchase decision process. The main motive for them to purchase new fashion apparel is to look attractive and stylish. In other words, we can say that personal appearance and attractive looks matter a lot for them. They are mostly involved in giving their style statements, and they considered themselves as more knowledgeable about fashion compared to others. Moreover, innovators rely heavily on the latest news and fashion shows available in catalogs and TV programs for updated their fashion wardrobe.

As far as purchase behavior of innovators is concerned, they prefer the specialty stores and for them, fashionable apparel is the most important attribute to purchase any fashion apparel. So we can say that innovators are very choosey about their selection of store for purchasing the apparel and as found

previously they are more concern about the fashionable and attractive look.

In terms of disposal behavior of innovators, the duration to wear any fashion apparel is not fixed and the majority of them give their used clothes to friends or relative always. So we can say that innovators believe in the optimum use of their fashion apparel in a way that after their use of apparel they give it to others so that they can also wear.

For non-innovators, the main motive for the purchase of fashion apparel was found to be sales and promotions. Non-innovators were found to be more price-conscious in their decision to purchase the fashion apparel. Also, they take advice from other women about latest fashion and style. They also learn about latest fashion by observing other women who are fashionable and stylish. Moreover, for purchase they often go to Department stores and are more concerned about the quality of the apparel. From this, we can say that as non-innovators are less involved in the frequent purchase of apparels, they prefer their apparel to be long-lasting and of good quality so that they can retain it for a longer time. As far as, duration to wear any fashion apparel is concerned, non-innovators are discarded their fashion apparel based on their favorability of that particular fashion apparel. And it was found that majority of the non-innovators always save their used apparel for future use. Hence we can conclude that they did not believe in discarding their used apparel. Hence, the conclusions from this study can be very useful for the fashion apparel industry. The fact that, the life cycle of fashion items is shorter for fashion innovators than for non-fashion innovators recommends that fashion innovators should be accepted as a target of the fashion market. In order to please fashion innovators, fashion designer and owners should make an attempt to establish new fashion items. For this, fashion designers and manufacturers should know the fashion consumption behavior of the consumers in terms of how they plan to purchase, what and where they purchase and how they dispose of their apparel. Thus, this study will make a small contribution in the above-discussed area.

VI. APPENDIX: THE QUESTIONNAIRE

A. Part 1: Fashion Innovativeness Scale

(Please rank the following statements on a five-point scale with 1= strongly disagree to 5= strongly agree)

1. In general, I am among the last in my circle of friends to buy new fashion apparel when it appears.
2. If I hear that a new style of fashion apparel was available in a store, I am usually interested enough to buy it.
3. Compared to my friends I own few new fashion garments.
4. I will buy new fashion garments, even if I have not heard of the fashion yet.
5. In general, I am the last in my circle of friends to know the names of the latest fashions and styles of apparel.
6. I know the names of new fashion designers before other people do.

(Note: The positively worded items, Q.1, 3, and 5, are reverse scored and the six-item scores added to form the total innovativeness score.)

B. Part 2: Fashion Consumption Behavior

1. Section 1: Pre-purchase behavior

1. What motives you the most to purchase fashion apparel (put a tick).
 - Personal enjoyment
 - Social occasions
 - Seasonal changes
 - Sale season
 - For latest style/fashion
2. Which is the most important source for you, to get the information about fashion apparel? (Put a tick).
 - Catalogues
 - Observation from social gatherings and parties
 - Store window display
 - Magazines
 - Friends
 - Fashion shows or Fashion TV
 - Salespersons
 - Family members
 - Internet
 - Fashion experts
 - Advice from other women

2. Section 2: Purchase behavior

3. From where you usually purchase your fashion apparel very often (put a tick)?
 - Department store
 - Discount store
 - Specialty store
 - Local brand store
 - Online shops
4. Which attribute of fashion apparel is most important for you, when you actually purchase it?
 - Fitting
 - Quality
 - Brand
 - Price
 - Comfort
 - Fashionable
 - Color
 - Pattern

3. Section 3: Post-purchase behavior

5. How long do you wear your any fashion apparel?
 - Less than 1 year
 - Between 1 year to 2 year
 - Between 2 year to 3 year
 - More than 3 years
 - It is not fixed
 - Depends on the favorability of the apparel
6. In general what you do with the fashion apparel, which you stopped wearing? Please indicate for each of the following actions listed below whether you always, often, sometimes, or never. (Give one number for each- 1 for always, 2 for often, 3 for sometimes and 4 for never)
 - Donate it
 - Save it because of some emotional attachment
 - Save it to wear in the coming years
 - Give it to relatives or friends
 - Throw it away
 - Recycle it
 - Sell it at a second-hand price

REFERENCES

- [1] Baumgarten, S.A. (1975). The innovative communicator in the diffusion process. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 12, 12-18.
- [2] Robertson, T. S. (1971). *Innovative Behavior and Communication*. New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston, Inc.
- [3] Tigert, D. J., Ring, L. J., and King, C. W. (1976). Fashion involvement and buying behavior. In B. B. Anderson (ed) *Advances in Consumer Research*. Cincinnati, OH: Association for consumer Research, 46-52.
- [4] Robertson, T. S. (1971). *Innovative Behavior and Communication*. New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston, Inc.
- [5] Levitt, T. (1965). Exploit the product life cycle. *Harvard Business Review*, 43, 81-94.
- [6] Goldsmith, R.E. & Hofacker, C.F. 1991, 'Measuring consumer innovativeness'. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, vol. 19, pp. 209-221.
- [7] Kotler, P., et al. (2009), *Marketing Management*, 1st European, Pearson Prentice Hall, Essex.
- [8] Diamond E. (2012). *Fashion Retailing: A Multi-Channel Approach*. USA: Pearson Education Inc.